

TARGETING TUMORS WITH NANOVACCINES: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF IMMUNE ACTIVATION, COMPOSITION, AND THERAPEUTIC STRATEGIES

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DOI: <https://doi.org/>

Received
30 MAY, 2025

Accepted
30 July, 2025

Published
21 August, 2025

ABSTRACT

The immune system evolved to protect the host organism from external infections while discriminating between self and non-self-entities. Cancer, on the other hand, is difficult to treat because it involves genetic changes in the host's cells, leading to uncontrolled proliferation and evasion of immune surveillance mechanisms. Cancer immunotherapy seeks to teach the immune system to recognize and kill altered cancer cells. The science of cancer immunotherapy has expanded dramatically in recent decades, with therapeutic vaccines appearing as a potential method, either alone or combined with other immunotherapies like immune checkpoint blockade therapy or adoptive cell treatment. This review explores the structure, methods, types, benefits, and limitations of nanovaccines in cancer treatment. A literature review spanning recent research articles on Nano vaccines was conducted through various authenticated public databases to gather information for such a comprehensive compilation. Nanomedicine offers a novel approach to improve the efficacy of these vaccinations by delivering molecular, cellular, or subcellular vaccines to lymphoid tissues and cells. This customized delivery technique attempts to increase the potency and duration of anti-tumor immune responses while minimizing side effects. Despite their potential, cancer vaccinations have shown poor success in clinical trials. **Keywords:** Adherence, Non-Adherence, Immunosuppressant, Liver Transplant.

KEYWORDS: Cancer immunotherapy Adjuvants Nanocarriers; mRNA nanovaccine

INTRODUCTION

Since the pioneering work of Edward Jenner in the year 1796, the practice of vaccination has assumed a pivotal role in the prophylaxis of numerous diseases and the enhancement of public health. A vaccine refers to a formulation that is delivered to provoke the immune system's response to a particular pathogenic entity or illness. Vaccines generate appropriate immune responses against diseases but have

limitations such as limited efficacy, low stability, and the need for multiple doses. To overcome these problems nano-vaccines offer a promising solution providing improved immunogenicity, stability, and patient compliance through their nano-sized range and precise antigen presentation. Nano-vaccines represent an innovative class of immunological preparations that utilize nanoparticles (NPs) as

vehicles and/or immunological adjuvants. Various kinds of nanoparticles containing different foreign or pathogenic antigens can lessen the requirement for booster doses and also assist in overcoming immunotolerance. Nano vaccines have demonstrated great potential in preventing diseases such as malaria, acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS), cancer, influenza, and tuberculosis, due to their unique properties (1).

Cancer constitutes a pathological condition characterized by the unregulated proliferation of certain cellular entities within the organism, which subsequently disseminate to various anatomical sites. Despite significant advances in cancer detection and understanding, traditional treatment options remain unchanged. Radiation therapy, surgical resection, and chemotherapy are common therapies, however, in many cases, these treatments fail and result in tumor recurrence or metastasis, demanding a different approach. From past studies, it is revealed that cancer immunotherapy plays critical role in treatment of patients, diagnosed by cancer (2). Various methods for modifying the immune system to treat cancer have been introduced, out of these vaccines on cancer is significant method. These vaccines are designed to induce powerful anti-tumor immune responses, target tumor cells specifically with minimum damage to healthy cells, and establish immunological memory against tumor antigens (3)(4). Cancer vaccines are being developed to address the limitations of cancer treatment, one intriguing solution is to employ nanoparticles (NPs) as delivery vehicles to enhance antigen presentation to effector lymphocytes and increase antigen delivery to APCs (antigen-presenting cells) (5). The basic goals of nano vaccines in cancer treatment are to trigger anti-tumor immune reactions while inhibiting immunosuppressive responses in the tumor microenvironment (6). Nanocarriers encapsulate antigens, improving their stability and preventing degradation, adjuvants can also help to improve the vaccine's immunogenicity and stability. Some nanoparticles (NPs) are designed to transfer antigens to the cytoplasm, enhancing anti-tumor responses of "CD8+ cytotoxic T lymphocyte. Dendritic cells possess the capacity to proficiently exhibit internalized antigens on

major histocompatibility complex (MHC) I molecules this phenomenon is referred to as cross-presentation (7). Surface alterations to NPs can elicit humoral and B cell-dependent responses, and utilizing polyvalent antigens on the nanoparticle surface can aid in targeted immunomodulation (8). The purpose of this review article is to provide an overview of nano-vaccines, including their properties, types of vaccines, nanocarriers, and adjuvants. Additionally, it summarizes the most recent research on the use of nano-vaccines in cancer prevention and therapy, as well as their disadvantages and advantages as a therapeutic approach (9).

Methodology

A comprehensive literature search was conducted to gather most relevant and most recent studies on nano-vaccines and their application in cancer prevention and therapy. Databases searched include PubMed, Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science. The search terms used were "nano-vaccines," "nanoparticles," "cancer immunotherapy," "cancer vaccines," "immunogenicity," "adjuvants," and "tumor microenvironment."

NANOVACCINE DELIVERY ROUTES

Nanotechnology has led to the development of advanced vaccines that utilize nanoparticles for improved delivery and efficacy (10). Nanoparticles can encapsulate or conjugate antigens on their surface, protecting them from degradation and enhancing immune cell targeting. These nano-carriers exhibit adjuvant properties that activate immune cells for more effective vaccine development (11). Strategies include controlled antigen release, stability improvement, and decoration with specific ligands targeting dendritic cell receptors. Incorporating immune-stimulatory molecules like α -Galactosylceramide (α -GalCer) enhances antigen-specific T-cell responses (12). Delivery routes of nano vaccines are explained in **Figure 1**. Nano-vaccines targeting invariant natural killer T-cells (iNKT) have demonstrated strong immune responses, indicating their potential for managing viral diseases. Liposomes co-encapsulating antigens and α -GalCer have shown significant IgG production and cellular immune responses, highlighting the role of

nano-vaccines in enhancing immune reactions (13).

Figure 1: Nano-carrier delivery routes enhanced by nanoparticles addition.

ACTIVATION OF IMMUNE RESPONSE BY NANOVACCINES

The innate immune system recognizes foreign particles such as nanoparticles through pattern-recognition receptors, triggering cellular uptake and immunomodulatory events. Nanoparticle properties like size, shape, and surface charge affect interactions with immune cells and impact cellular uptake pathways and immunoregulatory outcomes (14). Once internalized, dendritic cells present antigens to T-cells, initiating antigen-specific immune responses. Nanoparticles have ability to enhance antigen cross-presentation and induce cytotoxic T-lymphocyte responses essential for combating viral infections. Modifying adjuvants to enhance cytosolic delivery has shown improved CD8⁺ T-cell immunity (13).

COMPOSITION OF NANOVACCINE

Vaccines are produced by the incorporation of live or dead microbes. Vaccines provide immunity against infection by activating the immune system. However, as the spread of more and more infections and diseases has

increased, the necessity for formulation of the new vaccines has also grown. The application of nanotechnology in vaccinology emerged as a crucial step in enhancing immunogenicity, leading to the coining of the term nanovaccinology. Composition of nanovaccine is illustrated in Figure 2. Nanoparticle in vaccines works basically by enhancing the antigen processing and activating the immune system effectively. The efficacy of nano-vaccine is that they can easily penetrate the cellular component because of their small size and induces both humoral and cellular mediated response (15). Nano-vaccines are composed of molecular or nano adjuvants, nanocarriers and antigens. Many nanoparticles have been discovered that can act as immunomodulatory, which enables them to work as nanoadjuvants (16). Many nanomaterials are studied that can act as carrier for nano-vaccine. These are synthetic nanocarriers, biogenic nanocarriers, and semisynthetic nanocarriers. First, the components of nano vaccines will be discussed and then the function of those components.

Figure 2: Composition of Nano-vaccine.

● **ANTIGEN**

Nanovaccines employ nanoparticles to enhance both antigen delivery mechanisms and immune system responses because they function through advanced vaccine technology. Nanoparticles provide vaccines with enhanced cellular uptake thus activating an immune response that produces both antibody-based and T-cell-based protection. The three basic components in a nanovaccine consist of three fundamental elements. Nanovaccines integrate antigens which activate immunity with nanocarriers that protect antigens during delivery and nanoadjuvants which increase immune system responses. Multiple types of nanomaterials including liposomes and polymers and natural vesicles serve as both carriers and adjuvants to develop efficient and safer vaccines (17).

● **NEOANTIGENS**

Neoantigen are type of tumor antigen produced by non-synonymous somatic mutations or irregular gene expression which allows T cells to recognize them as foreign

proteins (18). Since neoantigen are non-self, they can easily be recognized by the immune

system, which can trigger the immune response. This is why neoantigens can be used as cancer vaccines to trigger the tumor-selective antitumor immune responses.

● **ADJUVANTS**

Vaccines receive adjuvants as additional substances which improve their effectiveness by boosting immunological reaction intensity. Adjuvants trigger the body's immediate defense system (innate immunity) as their first step to establish lasting protection (adaptive immunity) (16). The immune response functions better when exposed to delivery system adjuvants that include aluminum salts as well as emulsions and liposomes and virosomes because they slowly release antigens for better immune cell uptake. Among all vaccine additives aluminum-based adjuvants act as efficient antigen transporters and trigger robust antibody responses effectively (19). Additional adjuvants function as immune stimulators along with cytokines and STING agonists alongside toll-like receptor

(TLR) agonists including CpG and poly I:C. The activation of immune cells through these adjuvants produces both enhanced strength and enhanced specificity in immune reactions. Through collective action these vaccine components build superior disease protection mechanisms (20)

● NANOCARRIERS

Nanocarriers function as fundamental ingredients of nano-vaccines by enhancing vaccine delivery efficiency. Nanocarriers function through their minuscule size which creates extensive surface area capacity to transport larger amounts of vaccines or proteins or genetic materials. The vaccine delivery systems link vaccine compounds to precise molecular trackers that direct the vaccines to vital tissues and cells (21). Nanocarriers enhance vaccine uptake by cells and amplify the vaccine's therapeutic potential. Scientists use nanocarriers during cancer therapy to transport vaccines directly to immune cells which helps the body produce enhanced tumor-fighting immunity. The production of nanocarriers uses natural materials alongside synthetic materials and mixed combinations of materials (22).

TYPES OF NANOCARRIERS

Nano-carriers are used for efficient delivery of drugs especially for cancer immunotherapy for delivery of vaccines (23). Details about the recent progress in the development of nano-carriers used for cancer immunotherapy are discussed below:

1. BIOGENIC NANOCARRIERS:

Biological nano-carriers contain biological entities such as biological molecules. They are beneficial as they have the potential for great biocompatibility and biodegradability and less toxicity. Exosomes and OMVs (outer membrane vesicles) are examples of biological nano-carriers. Exosomes, which are carriers ranging from size 30-150 nm contain the capability of vaccine delivery efficiently. They are secreted by T cells, tumor cells, B cells, and APCs. Based on their cell origin Exosomes may be immuno-stimulatory and immunosuppressive, hence having potential applications in cancer immunotherapy and autoimmune diseases respectively. OMVs are

another example of biogenic nano-carriers potentially used for cancer immunotherapy. They are naturally prepared by an outer membrane of gram-negative bacteria so that they can communicate with themselves and also with other microorganisms in the environment (24). They have a diameter of 50-250 nm and thus can be used as great carriers for efficient lymph node homing and intracellular delivery into APCs (25). Till now, OMVs have been studied for developing bacterial vaccines and more recently for therapeutic vaccines (26)

2. SEMI-BIOGENIC NANOCARRIERS

These semi-synthetic nano-carriers are formed by combining biogenic and synthetic components, having features of both biogenic and synthetic nano-carriers. They are biocompatible and have low toxicity. Like synthetic NPs, they are easier to manufacture on a large scale. Cell membrane-coated nano-carriers, particularly Cancer cell membrane-coated NPs that contain cancer cell membrane antigens are used for drug delivery thus offering a platform for cancer nano-vaccines (27).

The use of self-generated protein-based nanoparticles constructed from albumin facilitates both vaccine residence time in the body while enhancing immune cell uptake which results in improved T cell activation. The delivery of cancer vaccines through synthetic HDL nanodiscs demonstrates effective results because these nanoscale structures replicate natural protein behavior (28). The "hitchhiking" delivery technique employs lipid fragments which bond with body albumin substances to transport antigen and immune enhancing substances to lymph nodes. The vaccine delivery method using lipid particles improves anti-tumor protection by both enhancing the vaccine's reach to immune cells and enhancing immune response in the human body (29).

3. SYNTHETIC NANOCARRIERS

Manufactured Nanocarriers function as vaccine-delivery devices which find special use in cancer immunotherapy applications. Two common nanoparticle vaccines made from PLGA help trigger powerful T cell responses while posing minimal safety risks. The biodegradable phospholipid-layered structures

known as liposomes employ two delivery mechanisms to transport antigens either inside their walls or on their exterior and improve immunity function (30). All types of nano-carriers are explained in Table 1. The use of inorganic nanoparticles as drug carriers stands

out because these materials demonstrate high accessibility to immune cells leading to effective tumor growth reduction when combined with antigen targets (29).

Table 1: Distinct types of Nano-carriers.

Type	Description	Examples	Key Features / Benefits
Biogenic Nanocarriers	- Derived from biological sources like cells or bacteria	Exosomes, OMVs	High biocompatibility, biodegradable, less toxic, immune modulatory
	- Exosomes: 30-150 nm, secreted by T cells, B cells, tumor cells, APCs		Can be immunostimulatory or immunosuppressive depending on origin
	- OMVs: 50-250 nm, from Gram-negative bacteria		Efficient lymph node targeting, used in bacterial and therapeutic vaccines
Semi-Biogenic Nanocarriers	Hybrid of biological and synthetic components	Cancer cell membrane-coated nanoparticles	Combine benefits of both; good biocompatibility, low toxicity, scalable manufacturing
			Present tumor antigens, useful in cancer nanovaccines
Synthetic Nanocarriers	Fully artificial nanomaterials designed for vaccine delivery	Liposomes, PLGA (polymer NPs), Inorganic NPs	High control over design, customizable surface, tunable degradation
	- PLGA: biodegradable polymer used for T cell-based cancer vaccine delivery		Stimulates strong immune responses, low immunotoxicity
	- Liposomes: phospholipid-based spherical vesicles		Can encapsulate/conjugate antigens; boost antigen-specific CTL response
	- Inorganic NPs (e.g., gold, silica)		Functionalized easily, taken up by immune cells, suppress tumor growth

STING AGONIST-BASED NANOVACCINES

A signaling molecule, called STING, is attached to the endoplasmic reticulum and plays a role in controlling transcription of several genes that are involved in the defense of the host organism. When STING detects cyclic dinucleotides (CDNs) it automatically causes

the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines and interferons (TYPE-1) (31) The discovery of STING indicates that it is involved in many biological as well as pathological activities. STING is an essential component of the innate immune system and plays a crucial role of in fighting against many bacterial pathogens, viral pathogens (32) and eukaryotic pathogens (17).

CDNs, that is basically is one of the class STING agonists, is studied for cancer immunotherapy. Studies revealed that, when CDNs binds with STING and results in the structural reconfiguration of the signaling molecule (STING), the signaling pathway of STING gets activate (25). Moreover, CDNs are considered a crucial part of vaccination in cancer treatment. The vaccine has demonstrated exceptional therapeutic efficacy in tumor models of mice. Even though the vaccine's initial clinical trials did not demonstrate an apparent therapeutic benefit over a control group, but still it is anticipated that CDN-based vaccinations will have a great deal of potential for cancer immunotherapy if formulations or clinical trial designs are optimized (5).

NEOANTIGEN VACCINE

In contrast to healthy cells, tumor neoantigens are produced by genetic events like somatic mutations. Such cell-specific presence makes neoantigens appealing target for development of cancer vaccines, since inoculation against cancer explicit neoantigens can possibly bypass peripheral as well as central mechanism of triggering immune system to limit hazard of prompting autoimmunity. Simultaneously, vaccines that are based on neoantigen are prepared by mRNA/DNA or long peptide (proteins) that are synthetically prepared by researchers (25).

In current clinical trials, it was determined that neoantigens uses a smooth workflow of genomic sequencing of normal cells, cancer cells and proteome analysis. With the aid of bioinformatics somatic mutations can be identified easily. Neoantigen immunogenicity is validated by in vitro technique and we get validated neoantigens in result (33). Finally, after getting validated neoantigens we achieve neoantigen vaccines for corresponding patients (34).

ARTIFICIAL APCS

Antigen-presenting cells (APCs) such as dendritic cells and macrophages as well as B cells begin the body's immune activation by displaying antigens to T and B cells. Antigen

processing cells (APCs) use MHC-II molecules to show antigens while activating the immune system. The FDA has approved PROVENGE as a prostate cancer vaccine that utilizes the patient's dendritic cells (autologous DCs) to fight cancer (35). The vaccines delivered promising results yet they proved costly and laborious because they depended on scarce materials from individual patients. Scientists developed artificial APCs (aAPCs) to overcome these difficulties because researchers can design controlled versions of these artificial antigen-presenting cells (36). The designers embedded special peptides that bind T-cell receptors to initiate T cell activation. Their design capabilities enable researchers to improve immunotherapy delivery by adjusting their properties. Together with the ability to create large APC batches they offer potential for cancer treatment. These therapies can be programmed to fight cancer cells of particular types (8). Types of Nano vaccines are introduced in Table 2.

COMBINATION IMMUNOTHERAPIES

To treat cancer at multiple levels, combination immunotherapy has proven instrumental because of its synergistic potential. An example is that of overcoming abscopal effect via the use of AC-NPs. The tumors were radiated and then their antigens were bound to Antigen-Capturing NPs coated with reactive chemical groups. These AC-NPs were transported to other tumors and treated them as well with high efficacy (37).

Another example is that of photodynamic therapy (PDT) combined with customized NPs having biodegradable mesoporous silica with a photosensitizer E6 and CpG. This combination overcame the shortcomings of PDT alone which was insufficient in removing all tumors and eliciting an antitumor response that could eliminate tumor relapse (38). Hence, cancer-based vaccines with antigens and adjuvants can treat cancer better when combined with other types of therapeutic strategies (1).

Table 2: Types of Nano-vaccines and their applications.

Type of Nano Vaccine	Key Feature	Purpose / Application
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1. mRNA Nano Vaccine	Encapsulates mRNA in lipid nanoparticles	Induces antigen production inside host cells
2. STING Agonist-Based	Delivers STING pathway activators using nanocarriers	Enhances innate immunity and antigen presentation
3. Neoantigen Vaccine	Uses patient-specific tumor antigens in nanoparticles	Personalized cancer immunotherapy
4. Artificial APCs (aAPCs)	Mimic antigen-presenting cells using nano- or micro-particles	Directly stimulate T-cell responses
5. Combination Immunotherapies	Combines nanovaccines with immune checkpoint inhibitors or adjuvants	Boosts overall immune response and therapeutic efficacy

CHALLENGES OF NANOVACCINES IN CANCER TREATMENT

Due to low immunogenicity and high heterogeneity of tumors, immunotherapeutic approach to treat cancer has proven difficult. Furthermore, T cells can be exhausted due to their upregulation which causes tumor recurrence (6). Other limitations involve inherent RNA instability, hindered expression of MHC by tumor, dwindled T cells cytotoxicity, along with costly and complicated protocols. However, the incorporation of immune checkpoint blockers improves the therapeutic approach (28).

CONCLUSION

In the light of conclusion, we would like to say that the use of nano-vaccines in immunotherapy to target intricate and complex diseases like cancer has proven to be another breakthrough in medical advancements. Customization and high specificity allow nano-vaccines to stimulate an advanced immune attack at tumors. Additionally, combination therapies are becoming more emergent as they provide a synergistic approach to overcome the drawbacks of any individual technique. Further work needs to be done to understand delivery of nano-vaccines and their intricate relationship with natural cells in the body along with tumors. Lastly, different tumor models should be employed to clinically assess the effectiveness of nano-vaccines.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to *Kohinoor Industries, Small Industrial Estate, Harappa Road, Sahiwal, 57000* for their valuable support and encouragement during the preparation of this review article.

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